

D3.6. Complete prototypes of US probe (10 prototypes)

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About ThrombUS+

Deep vein thrombosis (DVT) is the formation of a blood clot within the deep veins, most commonly those of the lower limbs, causing obstruction of blood flow. In 50% of people with DVT, the clot eventually breaks off and travels to the lung to cause pulmonary embolism. Clinical assessment of DVT is notoriously unreliable because up to 2/3 of DVT episodes are clinically silent and patients are symptom free even when pulmonary embolism has developed. Early diagnosis of DVT is crucial and despite the progress made in ultrasound imaging and plethysmography techniques, there is a need for new methods to enable continuous monitoring DVT diagnosis at the point of care.

ThrombUS+ brings together an interdisciplinary team of industrial, technology, regulatory, social science and clinical trial experts to develop a novel wearable diagnostic device for point-of-care, operator free, continuous monitoring in patients with high DVT risk. The device will combine autonomous, AI driven DVT detection based on a novel wearable ultrasound hardware, impedance plethysmography and light reflection rheography for immediate detection of blood clot formation in the lower limb. Activity and other physiological measurements will be used to provide a continuous assessment of DVT risk and support DVT prevention via serious gaming. The aggregated data will drive an intelligence decision support unit that will provide accurate monitoring and alerts. Extended reality will be used to guide experts to design exercises and patients to use the device optimally.

ThrombUS+ is intended for use by postoperative patients in the ward, during long surgical operations, cancer patients or otherwise bedridden patients at home or in care units, and women during pregnancy and postpartum. ThrombUS+ will use big data sets for AI training collected in the project via 3 large scale clinical studies and will validate the outcome in the clinical setting via 1 early feasibility study and 1 multi-center clinical trial.

Deliverable D3.6 Description

The deliverable corresponds to the output of task T3.6 – Complete prototypes of US probe (10 prototypes). The objective of T3.6 is the development and manufacturing of ten (10) fully integrated wearable ultrasound prototypes by combining all components developed during WP3, namely the ultrasound probes, the beamformer, and the tissue actuator, along with their accompanying software.

During T3.6, the ultrasound probes produced by Vermon and Fraunhofer, respectively, were packaged in a complete ultrasound system, utilizing the beamformer produced by TELEMED, ensuring suitability for imaging evaluation and suitable for wearable purposes. In addition, the ultrasound system is combined with the wearable tissue actuator to achieve operator-independent compression ultrasonography.

The deliverable presents ten (10) completed prototypes ready for final integration into the ThrombUS+ system, to perform the compression duplex ultrasound DVT monitoring method. Prototype repeatability was evaluated and is presented in this deliverable. KTU led the integration and the final characterization of the final completed devices.

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Terms and Definitions

Term	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CDUS	Compression Duplex Ultrasound
CHI	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Central Hub & Intelligence Module
CUS	Compression Ultrasound Imaging
CSW	C-shell type Semirigid Wearable
DoA	Description of Action
EAC	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Electronic Actuator Controller
EC	European Commission
EIM	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Electrical Impedance Module
EIP	Electrical Impedance Plethysmography
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
LAM	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Limb Activity Module
LRM	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Light Rheography Module
LRR	Light Reflection Rheography
ML	Machine Learning
PPG	Photoplethysmography
RUCs	Reference Use Cases
US	Ultrasound
USM	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Ultrasound Monitoring Module
VOP	Venous Occlusion Plethysmography
WAM	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Wearable Actuator Module
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader
WSN	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Wearable Sensors Network
WTE	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Wearable Tetrapolar Electrode
WTC	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Wearable Thigh Cuff
WUSD	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Wearable Ultrasound Device

Executive Summary

This deliverable outlines the assembly and integration process carried out on the ThrombUS+ compression ultrasound device, with a focus on the integration and verification of the Ultrasound Imaging Module (USM) and the Wearable Actuator Module (WAM) to enable operator-independent monitoring for Deep Vein Thrombosis (DVT).

A total of ten complete system prototypes were finalized, each comprising an ultrasound probe, beamformer, and wearable actuator module. During prototype selection, the VERMON LA6.0/128 linear array transducer was selected as the most suitable probe.

The USM performance was evaluated through inter-prototype variability testing in both B-mode and Color-Flow Doppler imaging. Results demonstrated highly consistent imaging performance across all ten prototypes. In B-mode, visual and quantitative analyses showed negligible differences. In Doppler mode, minor variations in flow detection sensitivity were observed, confirming uniform functionality across units.

The WAM enables controlled tissue compression using the Electronic Actuator Controller (EAC) and a redesigned C-shell semi-rigid wearable (CSW).

In conclusion, the ThrombUS+ prototypes demonstrated equivalent, reliable, and reproducible performance, with negligible inter-unit variability. Based on these results, four systems have been allocated for manual ultrasonography in Clinical Study B1, while six fully integrated wearable systems are prepared for integration into the complete ThrombUS+ system within Work Package WP6 and for automated monitoring in Clinical Study C, supporting the project's readiness for clinical evaluation.

1. Introduction

To achieve operator-independent compression ultrasonography, the Compression Ultrasound Subsystem (CUS) consists of two main parts: (1) an ultrasound module (USM) for B- and Doppler mode imaging, and (2) a wearable actuator module (WAM) that provides controlled compression of the thigh tissues, including veins and arteries (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The ThrombUS+ subsystem for operator-independent Compression Ultrasonography: only the highlighted modules are used in this scenario.

Both modules include hardware and software components, which are described in more detail¹ and below.

– Ultrasound Module (USM) components:

- A linear multi-element ultrasonic transducer used for automated vein scanning, with 128 elements of conventional piezocomposite technology and/or 96 elements by CMUT technology, ensuring scanning depth of at least 8 cm.
- Beamformer, connected to the ultrasonic transducer and to CHI via a USB cable for power supply and data transmission. Beamformer has associated firmware and SDK for Windows OS.

– Wearable Actuator Module (WAM) components:

- C-shell-type semirigid wearable (CSW): a wearable submodule designed to house a detachable ultrasound transducer and integrate air bladders for performing compression ultrasound imaging (CUS) to assess blood clot formation and blood flow in the lower limbs.

¹ Cesana, J., Annunziata, S., Moltani, L. A., Didaskalou, S., Jurkonis, R., Marozas, V., Lukosevicius, A., Schubert, F., & Balling, S. (2025). ThrombUS+ D2.4: Architectural design of the strap and sock wearable (v2.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17642398>

- Wearable thigh cuff (WTC): a wearable submodule designed to house an air bladder for performing thigh tissue compression.
- Electronic actuator controller (EAC): manages the level of tissue and vein compression using a piezo-disc silent air pump and pressure sensors.

The illustration of the developed components is presented in the figure Figure 2 below.

Figure 2. The components developed for the CUS subsystem.

More details on the wearable strap about its textile part are reported in deliverable D4.6. Practical recommendations on the usage of prototyped CUS devices in planned clinical studies are provided in Annex 6.

2. Ultrasound imaging module

This chapter presents the main components of the ultrasound imaging module (USM) and the results obtained from inter-prototype uniformity testing. The objective of this study was to ensure that the ultrasound system module (USM) prototypes demonstrated reliable performance and reproducible behavior with respect to imaging capabilities in both B-mode and Doppler imaging. A total of 20 images of a tissue-mimicking phantom were acquired (10 in B-mode and 10 in combined B-mode and Doppler-mode) for subsequent visual and quantitative assessment of imaging characteristics. The results revealed very low inter-prototype variability and confirmed that the USM prototypes are ready for clinical experiments.

2.1. Components of the ultrasound imaging module

In the initial stage of testing of the developed USM components, two delivered prototypes of linear arrays—VERMON's LA6.0/128² and Fraunhofer's AC1655³—were evaluated to identify the most suitable transducer for subsequent clinical studies. The main characteristics provided by the manufacturers of both probes are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Main characteristics of the ultrasound probes.

Parameter	Probe LA6.0/128 (Vermon)	AC1655 (Fraunhofer)
Type	Linear	Linear
Number of elements	128	96
Pitch	0.3 mm	0.2 mm
Central frequency	5.90 MHz	3.6 MHz
Bandwidth*	86.3 % (3.35 MHz – 8.44 MHz)	96 %
Sensitivity Variation	1.6 dB	Not Specified
Cable length	2 m	2 m
Max Cable Diameter	6 mm	Not Specified

*The bandwidth measurements are done by producers and declared in the datasheets.

Both probes were connected to the Thrombus+ beamformer and tested under identical conditions. An aperture of eight active elements was used for each probe, and both were excited with the same pulse shape (a single negative half-period) at 4MHz. This excitation frequency was selected because the AC1655 exhibited its most favorable frequency response at this value⁴.

For signal acquisition, the probes were immersed in a water tank and positioned orthogonally to a flat metallic reflector at a fixed distance of 55mm. The excitation amplitude for the LA6.0/128 probe had to be reduced because the high reflection coefficient of the metallic target caused signal clipping at power levels only slightly above the minimum setting (–20dB, approximately –8V). Figure 3 shows the normalized spectra obtained from both probes.

² Legros M, Pousset N, Toffessi Siewe S, Boulay S, Voisin D, Raybaud G, Ultrasound Transducer Array Prototypes: Composite PZT technology, Deliverable 3.1, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 2 January 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14500724>

³ Völz U., Kircher M., Lange N., Ultrasound Transducer Prototypes: MEMS Technology, Deliverable 3.2, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 02 January 2025, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14540400>

⁴ Sakalauskas A, Prysiazniuk A, Novikov D, Ultrasound Transducer Control and Image Formation, Deliverable D3.4, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 31 March 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15113600>

Figure 3. Normalized spectra for AC1655 (brown) and LA6.0/128 (blue) using an identical excitation pulse shape at 4 MHz, with different excitation amplitudes.

The LA6.0/128 probe generates higher-frequency components and exhibits a substantially wider bandwidth compared with the AC1655 (see Figure 3). Time-domain signals (Figure 4) were also analyzed, and the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) was calculated for both probes.

Figure 4. Pulses recorded from a metallic reflector using both probes (LA6.0/128 and AC1655).

Visual inspection indicates that the AC1655 produces a higher noise level. Although the signal amplitudes appear comparable, it must be noted that the excitation amplitude differed by 20dB. The measured SNR for the LA6.0/128 was 36.18dB, whereas the AC1655 achieved 18.45dB.

In conclusion, the AC1655 probe demonstrates limited ability to generate higher-frequency spectral components (Figure 3). Its center frequency is approximately 3 MHz, and its –6 dB bandwidth spans only 1.5–4.5MHz—narrower than that of the LA6.0/128 (Figure 3). The AC1655 also exhibits a higher noise floor. Furthermore, the probes required different excitation amplitudes: the AC1655 operated at the maximum available level (0 dB), while the LA6.0/128 required a substantially reduced excitation (–20dB) due to its higher sensitivity.

Based on these comparative results, the LA6.0/128 was selected as the preferred probe. Ten LA6.0/128 and Telemed beamformer prototype pairs were further tested prior to clinical studies to verify and ensure inter-prototype uniformity.

The prototypes consist of ten ultrasound arrays LA6.0/128 developed by VERMON, beamformers provided by Telemed, and the supporting software required to operate the USM system. Ultrasound beamformers, the main technical characteristics are provided in Table 2.

Table 2. Main characteristics of the ultrasound beamformer⁵.

Parameter	Value
T/R Channels count	32
Maximal number of elements to drive	128
Dimensions (W × D × H)	111x111x30mm
Connection	Type-C to Type-C USB cable
Supported imaging modes	B, B + B, 4B, B + M, M, CFM, PDI, DPDI, Triplex
Delay precision (transmit)	6.25ns
Receive channel bandwidth	20MHz
Dynamic Range	102dB

Support for the beamformer and probe prototypes was integrated into the Telemed software system beginning with the Telemed Drivers Package 2.3.0b54, EchoWave II Package 4.3.1b75 (GUI), and SDK 4.3.1b71. The architecture of the Telemed software system is presented in Deliverable D3.4. Figure 5 presents several photographs of the USM prototype, showing all components both separately and when connected.

⁵ Sakalauskas A, Prysiazniuk A, Novikov D, Ultrasound Transducer Control and Image Formation, Deliverable D3.4, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 31 March 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15113600>

Figure 5. The USM prototype components: Right: LA6.0/128 probe (Vermon), middle; beamformer (Telemed) and left: USM module prototype connected to a laptop running EchoWave II software (Telemed).

2.2. Inter-prototype uniformity assessment of the ultrasound system module

2.2.1. Methodology for B-mode image assessment

In the initial stage, B-mode images were analyzed. The images were acquired using a tissue-mimicking phantom (model 054GS with embedded targets, CIRS, USA, Figure 6). The scanning operator positioned the probe at the same location on the phantom and used acoustic gel for coupling.

The principal imaging parameters were configured as follows: imaging depth of 50mm, transmit frequency of 9MHz, dynamic range of 72dB, gain set to 100%, acoustic power at 0dB, and high line density. A specific piecewise linear RGB colour map was applied to facilitate evaluation of the brightest and weakest echoes within the images. In this mapping, the brightest echoes were represented in red, the weakest echoes in light blue, and intermediate levels were displayed using a linear grayscale. The images were subjected to both visual inspection and quantitative analysis, with mean image intensity calculated across all 10 images obtained from the different USM prototypes.

Figure 6. Tissue-mimicking phantom used for testing the USM

2.2.2. Results of the B-mode assessment

Figure 7 presents a B-mode image acquired from one USM prototype, while **Error! Reference source not found.** in Annex 1 shows the corresponding results for all ten prototypes. Visual inspection of these images revealed no discernible differences, indicating that the prototypes exhibit consistent and comparable imaging performance.

Figure 7. Illustration of the B-mode tissue-mimicking phantom image obtained for one prototype.

Table 3 summarizes the quantitative results of the pixel mean intensity (I_p) and its deviation (S.D.) across the B-mode image of each prototype. The standard deviation in the second column [22.23 - 23.14] is attributable to the B-mode image nature, because of the different intensity objects observable in the phantom image (strong reflectors, weak echoes, and background) and scattering of phantom background material. The calculated standard deviation (column 3) of all I_p , equal to ± 3.46 across the images obtained from the 10 USM prototypes, indicates that imaging performance is consistent among the prototypes with deviation $< 3\%$ (obtained by $\frac{3.46}{118.38} * 100\% = 2.92\%$). The minor deviations observed are negligible and are likely attributable to variations in acoustic coupling or slight misalignment between the probe and the phantom.

In conclusion, the B-mode investigation demonstrated that all prototypes exhibited equivalent and uniform performance.

Table 3. Quantitative evaluation of overall mean image intensity and intensity deviation for all 10 ThrombUS+ ultrasound prototypes.

Prototype No.	$I_p \pm S.D.$	Mean \pm S.D.
1.	119.38 \pm 22.23	
2.	119.59 \pm 22.85	
3.	119.04 \pm 22.85	
4.	123.63 \pm 23.14	
5.	119.66 \pm 22.60	
6.	118.56 \pm 22.29	118.38 \pm 3.46
7.	114.99 \pm 22.92	
8.	110.27 \pm 22.32	
9.	120.42 \pm 22.81	
10.	118.29 \pm 22.47	

2.2.3. Methodology for the Doppler mode assessment

A colour Doppler sensitivity test was performed using the Doppler phantom 523A (CIRS, USA, Figure 8). By moving the transducer across the surface of this phantom, it is possible to change the distance to the blood vessel-simulating channel. The blood-mimicking fluid is flowing through the channel at a constant velocity of 25 cm/s. The testing operator finds the maximum distance at which flow is still detected.

Figure 8. Phantom used for testing the USM Doppler mode.

The principal imaging parameters for Doppler mode were configured as follows: pulse repetition frequency of 3.5kHz, gain set to 70%, acoustic power at 0dB, and transmit frequency of 5.3MHz. The resulting images were evaluated through both visual inspection and quantitative analysis, with measurements focused on the depth at which flow remained identifiable across all 10 images acquired from each of the USM prototypes.

2.2.4. Results of the Doppler mode assessment

Figure 9 presents one example of a combined B and Doppler mode image acquired from the USM prototype No. 1. The same test was performed for all 10 prototypes. All Doppler mode imaging results are presented in Annex 2. Visual inspection of these images indicated no discernible differences among them, demonstrating that the prototypes exhibit consistent and comparable imaging performance. Table 4 present Doppler sensitivity measurement quantitative results for all 10 prototypes.

Quantitative analysis revealed a minimal deviation of 1.37mm in sensitivity across the 10 prototypes. These findings confirm that the prototypes deliver consistent performance in combined B-mode and colour flow imaging.

In conclusion, the USM colour-mode investigation demonstrated that all prototypes exhibited equivalent and uniform performance, with only negligible inconsistency observed. The deviation is <3% (obtained by $\frac{1.37}{46.6} * 100\% = 2.94\%$).

Figure 9. Combined B and Doppler flow mode tissue-mimicking phantom image obtained for the prototype No. 1 (At the bottom left corner sensitivity measurement result is presented – 47.4 mm),

Table 4. Quantitative results of Doppler flow mode sensitivity.

Prototype No.	Sensitivity, mm	Mean ± S.D.
1.	47.4	
2.	46.0	
3.	45.8	
4.	50.1	
5.	46.8	
6.	45.5	46.6 ± 1.37
7.	45.4	
8.	46.1	
9.	46.3	
10.	46.6	

3. Wearable actuator module for tissue compression

The Wearable Actuator Module (WAM) is used by the CUS subsystem to apply controlled pressure to thigh tissues. It consists of an Electronic Actuator Controller (EAC) and a C-shell–type semi-rigid wearable (CSW). In WP3.6, the initially planned “Final Probe” concept evolved during implementation into several redesigned versions incorporating additional advanced features. Experimental results from WP3.5 indicated the need to

improve the wearable component that supports all accessories on the human thigh. Hardware production for bladder pressurization in the CDUS and VOP methods revealed the need to implement different pressurization profiles within a single hardware assembly. This chapter reports on the prototypes resulting from these redesigns and upgrades.

The components of the disassembled electronic actuator controller (EAC) are shown in Figure 10. Assembly of the electronic, pneumatic, and mechanical components was completed for ten EAC devices.

Figure 10. Components for tissue compression. Right: electronic, pneumatic, and mechanical components of electronic actuator component (EAC). Left; fully assembled electronic actuator controller (EAC) developed by KTU.

The semi-rigid C-shaped wearable has been redesigned (Figure 11) with several improvements, including a flexible material (previously rigid in D3.5), hollow sections in the frame to improve skin breathability (previously solid plastic), the use of biocompatible and skin-friendly materials, reduced fabric coverage to allow easier cleaning (in some cases, wiping the frame is sufficient), and the selection of a finer-grade Velcro hook material to reduce noise during detachment.

Figure 11. C-shaped wearable redesign solutions: Left: rigid design developed in WP3.3. Middle; the 3D model of a newly designed semi-flexible C-shaped wearable. Left; textiles designed by ComfTech.

Error! Reference source not found. in Annex 3 presents all electronic actuator controllers developed by KTU. **Error! Reference source not found.** in Annex 4 presents all C-shaped wearables and their components

developed by ComfTech. Practical assembly instructions and on-body mounting recommendations of the wearable CUS probe are provided in Annex 5.

3.1. Technical software for testing and controlling the CUS hardware

The software was developed to support the integrated operation of both the air pumping and imaging functions. Using this software, inter-prototype uniformity of all hardware units was verified experimentally. A representative final image (B-mode), acquired at a compression level of 120mmHg, together with the complete pressurization process, is shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12. Example of data registered with the CUS technical software.

Ultrasonography images were acquired using an integrated CUS hardware on a silicone phantom of the thigh tissues ("3B SONOtrain VEIN," 3B Scientific, Germany). Results of the EAC performance verification were collected using technical testing software for CUS. Pressure profiles characterizing EAC performance are presented in Section 4 of this deliverable.

To facilitate the development of CHI software, the EAC technical testing software was developed at KTU in parallel with the EAC hardware. The panel view of the EAC technical software is presented in Figure 13.

Figure 13. Illustration of the GUI of the technical software for testing and control of the EAC hardware.

3.2. Results of the EAC devices assessment

An example of recorded pressurization results in the reference chamber (760mL) is shown in Figure 14. Pressure was generated by two air pumps in the silent piezo-pump assembly (EAC No. 09). The maximum pressure reached was 149.96 mmHg, with pressure levels of 9.66 mmHg and 142.53 mmHg corresponding to 0.05 and 0.95 of the maximum, respectively. The time required to increase pressure from 0.05 to 0.95 of the maximum was 18.92 s.

Figure 14. Illustration of inflation (red line - first EAC channel) and (blue line – second EAC channel) profiles of the EAC device. Data points indicate the pressure levels: maximal Pint1 max and rising edge at levels 0.05Pint1,max to 0.95Pint1,max.

The pressure requested from the EAC is referred to as the target pressure. The EAC includes an internal sensor that measures the effective pressure in the pneumatic system and records real-time pressure values. Two pressure sensors are integrated into the EAC, one for each pressure channel. To describe the pressure exerted by the bladder on the soft tissues, the specific term interfacial pressure is introduced (see D3.5⁴ for

details). The interfacial pressure induced in the bladder and measured during operation serves as an indicator of the precision of EAC pressure control. For example, with EAC No. 3, the requested target pressure was 150 mmHg with a 1350 mW power supply applied to the piezo pumps. Verification measurements showed that the achieved, bladder-induced interfacial pressure was 149.90 ± 0.04 mmHg in the first pressure channel (Pint1) of the EAC. Accurate pressure control by the EAC was verified not only at the maximum compression level (Pint1). Five pressurization runs were recorded, and the pressure rise profiles were evaluated at the 0.95 level to assess repeatability in both EAC pressure channels (Pint1 and Pint2). The evaluation results at $0.95 P_{\text{int1,max}}$ and $0.95 P_{\text{int2,max}}$ are listed in Table 5.

The pressurization time was measured between the time points at which the pressure reached $0.05 P_{\text{int1,max}}$ and $0.95 P_{\text{int1,max}}$ in the first EAC pressure channel. The first and second EAC pressurization channels exhibited similar performance in terms of achieved pressure levels: Pint1 ranged from 136 to 143 mmHg, while Pint2 ranged from 139 to 150 mmHg. The corresponding pumping durations to reach these final pressures ranged from 16 to 23 seconds. All pressure rise data for the first and second pressure channels are summarized in Table 5.

Table 5. Performance results of EAC individual compression channels (P_{int1} and P_{int2}) in independent two-chamber pneumatic operation*.

EAC Serial No.	Target pressure (mmHg)	Pump power (mW)	Recording length (samples)	$P_{\text{int1,max}}$ (mmHg)	$0.95 * P_{\text{int1,max}}$ (mmHg)	$0.95 * P_{\text{int2,max}}$ (mmHg)	Compression time from $0.05 * P_{\text{int1,max}}$ to $0.95 * P_{\text{int1,max}}$ (seconds)
03**	150	1350	400	149.90 ± 0.04	142.79 ± 0.09	149.81 ± 0.23	16.77 ± 0.23
04	150	1350	400	149.82 ± 0.04	142.84 ± 0.14	146.74 ± 0.14	15.91 ± 0.57
05	150	1350	400	149.73 ± 0.03	142.78 ± 0.20	142.50 ± 0.29	17.58 ± 0.14
06	150	1350	400	149.82 ± 0.02	142.78 ± 0.08	142.51 ± 0.90	17.84 ± 0.07
07	150	1350	400	148.26 ± 0.76	141.95 ± 0.60	149.54 ± 0.22	22.72 ± 0.30
08	150	1350	400	149.85 ± 0.03	142.76 ± 0.14	142.57 ± 2.03	18.14 ± 0.09
09	150	1350	400	149.90 ± 0.03	142.64 ± 0.09	143.70 ± 0.90	19.42 ± 0.37
10	150	1350	400	149.94 ± 0.04	142.91 ± 0.26	138.50 ± 1.34	17.62 ± 0.37
11	150	1350	400	142.15 ± 16.79	135.53 ± 15.73	149.77 ± 0.16	21.83 ± 1.19
12	150	1350	400	149.90 ± 0.05	142.84 ± 0.17	143.11 ± 0.58	18.34 ± 0.06

* EAC-sampled pressure data and inflation time are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation, from five recordings ($n = 5$)

** EACs with serial numbers 01 and 02 were not extensively assessed because they were sent to partners immediately after production and initial tests, to facilitate integration tasks with other modules and minimize delays.

An example of the outflow pressure profile is shown in Figure 15, illustrating pressure release from the independent two reference chambers using the EAC device. The two lines are indicated, corresponding to the first and second pressure channels in EAC. The maximum pressure was 149.96 mmHg, with pressure levels of 107.2 mmHg and 2.9 mmHg corresponding to 0.9 and 0.1 of the maximum, respectively. The time required for pressure release from 0.9 to 0.1 of the maximum was 0.52 s.

Figure 15. Representative outflow pressure profiles (red line - first EAC channel) and (blue line - second EAC channel) of the EAC device. Data points indicate the pressure levels: initial maximal $P_{int1,max}$ and depressurizing edge at levels $0.9P_{int1,max}$ to $0.1P_{in}$.

From the pressure data extracted, numerical values describing the depressurization performance are listed in Table 6. From each EAC device, the target pressure in both channels was 150 mmHg.

Table 6. Results of decompression performance* with EAC independent channels P_{int1} and P_{int2} for the VOP method.

EAC Serial No.	Initial interfacial pressure maximum $P_{int1,max}$ (mmHg)	Pressure level $0.9*P_{int1,max}$ (mmHg)	Pressure level $0.1*P_{int1,max}$ (mmHg)	Compression time from $0.9*P_{int1,max}$ to $0.1*P_{int1,max}$ (seconds)	Pressure level $0.9*P_{int2,max}$ (mmHg)	Pressure level $0.1*P_{int2,max}$ (mmHg)
03**	150.10 ± 0.04	95.18 ± 16.21	9.31 ± 1.08	0.39 ± 0.08	92.13 ± 16.34	11.87 ± 0.77
04	150.08 ± 0.05	100.12 ± 15.89	9.85 ± 3.61	0.36 ± 0.05	98.80 ± 13.78	10.86 ± 2.93
05	150.04 ± 0.04	97.61 ± 10.28	8.55 ± 3.93	0.35 ± 0.05	90.87 ± 10.51	8.825 ± 3.74
06	150.05 ± 0.04	92.62 ± 17.87	7.32 ± 2.19	0.38 ± 0.05	90.38 ± 16.21	7.78 ± 3.34
07	149.04 ± 0.66	109.35 ± 12.20	8.09 ± 2.42	0.38 ± 0.05	101.50 ± 10.90	10.21 ± 2.67
08	150.08 ± 0.06	105.01 ± 10.21	7.98 ± 3.94	0.40 ± 0.07	101.18 ± 8.99	7.34 ± 3.07
09	150.04 ± 0.02	104.92 ± 18.57	3.89 ± 2.53	0.41 ± 0.01	100.39 ± 13.79	5.21 ± 2.92
10	150.14 ± 0.09	104.91 ± 14.14	8.06 ± 2.54	0.40 ± 0.06	101.60 ± 12.67	8.71 ± 2.37
11	142.55 ± 16.58	99.74 ± 23.14	8.32 ± 2.72	0.38 ± 0.05	102.27 ± 12.66	11.06 ± 1.09
12	150.07 ± 0.04	101.5 ± 19.42	7.53 ± 2.85	0.40 ± 0.04	97.28 ± 16.17	8.26 ± 2.63

* EAC-sampled pressure data and inflation time are expressed as mean ± standard deviation, from five recordings (n = 5)

** EACs with serial numbers 01 and 02 were not extensively assessed because they were sent to partners immediately after production and initial tests, to facilitate integration tasks with other modules and minimize delays.

The EAC depressurizes the first and second channels with similar performance. The pressure release was measured between time instances of 0.9 and 0.1 maximal interfacial pressure, which was 150 mmHg. The $0.9P_{\text{int1,max}}$ level was in the range 93 to 105 mmHg, and the level $0.1P_{\text{int1,max}}$ was in the range 8 to 10 mmHg. The time duration of this pressure drop is in the range of 0.35 to 0.41 seconds. All data about depressurizing is listed in Table 6. It should be noted that during the rapid depressurizing process, pressure sampling in EAC was triggered using ultrasonography images obtained via a beamformer. The rate in the beamformer was about 18 images per second, so the pressure data sampling interval was 56 milliseconds. The same rate of pressure data sampling was in both pressurizing and depressurizing of bladders.

4. Performance of the integrated compression ultrasonography probes

The in vivo verification of the automated final probe of the CUS method was found to be subject-dependent; therefore, CUS probe performance could be obscured by inter-subject variability. Uniform verification of the final probe performance can instead be carried out using a stable physical phantom. The biomechanical properties of the phantom were addressed in D3.5⁴ (Figures 24 to 26), where the choice of the vein model in the silicone phantom “3B SONOtrain VEIN” was justified based on in vivo recordings. The interfacial pressure–strain diagrams recorded from a group of subjects was adequately replicated using the “3B SONOtrain VEIN” silicone phantom⁶. A stable physical model helps to identify the inter-unit performance stability of produced CUS probes.

A stable physical model enables the identification of the inter-unit performance stability of the produced final probes. The phantom was used in a proprietary setup (see Annex 5) to eliminate application-related variability observed during the pilot experiments reported in D3.5⁴ (see Figure 23 in D3.5), where the silicone component could be arranged differently between probe applications. Representative images illustrating the intermediate moments of the vein model responding in the silicone phantom are shown in Figure 16.

The numerical data obtained from the silicone phantom are presented as time-dependent pressure and strain diagrams in Figure 17. The example image series was collected during a compression cycle, with corresponding image indices recorded simultaneously with pressure data. The registered tissue response is expressed numerically in terms of strain. Vertical stem markers could be included to indicate the indexing of images or time instances at which the intermediate images were recorded.

⁶ Affagard, J. S., Feissel, P., & Bensamoun, S. F. (2015). Identification of hyperelastic properties of passive thigh muscle under compression with an inverse method from a displacement field measurement. *Journal of biomechanics*, 48(15), 4081–4086. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbiomech.2015.10.007>

Figure 16. Example of image data acquired using a replica of the integrated WP3 hardware on the silicone phantom “3B SONOtrain VEIN” (3B Scientific, Hamburg, Germany). In the images pixel size is 0.1172 mm.

Figure 17. Example of numerical data registered using a replica of the integrated WP3 hardware on the silicone phantom “3B SONOtrain VEIN” (3B Scientific, Hamburg, Germany).

The compression ultrasonography (CUS) probes were assembled as sets consisting of a beamformer, transducer, EAC, and wearable components. The sets were assembled randomly, and all units were identified by serial numbers. The composition of the six assembled CUS probes is presented in the first four columns of Table 7. Six fully assembled CUS probes were verified, as only six beamformers with transducers were available and not allocated to routine (non-compression) ultrasonography preparations. Routine (manual) ultrasonography preparations using four beamformers and transducers are supervised by partners in Greece, together with clinical partners and image analysis experts, as part of the preparation for Clinical Study B.

Each CUS probe was applied to a silicone tissue phantom (“3B SONOtrain VEIN”) to emulate random application conditions. All six CUS probes were similarly applied to the silicone phantom (see Annex 5). The open CSW was positioned upward on a tabletop, and coupling gel was applied to the working surface of the ultrasound transducer inserted into the CSW. The phantom was then placed onto the transducer within the open CSW, and acoustic coupling was ensured by the weight of the silicone. Finally, the bladder was fixed to the CSW using Velcro straps. With closed CSW, the channel representing the vein lumen within the silicone material was filled with distilled water.

For each CUS probe application, compressions at 150 mmHg (target pressure) were repeated five times without changing the application conditions. In EAC, the air pumping power for the piezo-silent pumps assembly was set to 1390mW. In the CUS technical software, the total number of images ($n=450$) per compression was requested. The resulting CUS probe performance metrics are summarized in Table 7.

Table 7. Quantitative results* of the compression ultrasonography probe (Wearable CUS) on a silicone phantom.

Number of CUS Probe	Wearable serial number	EAC serial number	Beamformer; transducer serial numbers	Induced interfacial pressure $P_{int,max}$ (mmHg)	Pressure level $0.95 * P_{int,max}$ (mmHg)	Pressure level $0.05 * P_{int,max}$ (mmHg)	Compression time from $0.05 * P_{int,max}$ to $0.95 * P_{int,max}$ (sec)	Strain at $0.05 * P_{int,max}$, %	Strain at $0.95 * P_{int,max}$, %
1	CSW-12	No05	21278-251209-0006; 2886AF1007	149.06 ± 0.39	142.08 ± 0.29	7.64 ± 0.14	25.19 ± 0.29	0.67 ± 0.07	14.32 ± 0.43
2	CSW-11	No09	21278-251209-0005; 2886AF1013	149.90 ± 0.07	142.80 ± 0.09	7.66 ± 0.11	24.99 ± 0.83	0.91 ± 0.04	13.27 ± 0.04
3	CSW-12	No04	21278-251210-0010; 2886AF1017	149.86 ± 0.07	142.86 ± 0.13	7.62 ± 0.09	24.22 ± 0.50	0.16 ± 0.07	13.64 ± 0.17
4	CSW-11	No12	21278-251209-0008; 2886AF1016	150.03 ± 0.04	143.16 ± 0.08	7.64 ± 0.07	23.64 ± 0.96	0.26 ± 0.13	12.81 ± 0.45
5	CSW-12	No10	21278-251209-0007; 2886AF1016	150.13 ± 0.07	143.00 ± 0.17	7.66 ± 0.08	26.77 ± 0.79	0.38 ± 0.15	13.09 ± 0.13
6	CSW-11	No08	21278-251209-0009; 2886AF1015	149.79 ± 0.04	142.66 ± 0.13	7.55 ± 0.04	24.76 ± 0.54	0.42 ± 0.21	12.61 ± 0.44
1	CSW-12	No05	21278-251209-0006; 2886AF1007	149.06 ± 0.39	142.08 ± 0.29	7.64 ± 0.14	25.19 ± 0.29	0.67 ± 0.07	14.32 ± 0.43
2	CSW-11	No09	21278-251209-0005; 2886AF1013	149.90 ± 0.07	142.80 ± 0.09	7.66 ± 0.11	24.99 ± 0.83	0.91 ± 0.04	13.27 ± 0.04
3	CSW-12	No04	21278-251210-0010; 2886AF1017	149.86 ± 0.07	142.86 ± 0.13	7.62 ± 0.09	24.22 ± 0.50	0.16 ± 0.07	13.64 ± 0.17
4	CSW-11	No12	21278-251209-0008; 2886AF1016	150.03 ± 0.04	143.16 ± 0.08	7.64 ± 0.07	23.64 ± 0.96	0.26 ± 0.13	12.81 ± 0.45

* EAC-sampled pressure data and inflation time are expressed as mean ± standard deviation, from five recordings (n = 5)

5. Conclusions

Visual inspection and quantitative analysis of ultrasound module inter-prototype uniformity revealed only negligible differences among the prototypes, with mean intensity in B-mode images deviating by ± 3.46 and color Doppler flow mode sensitivity deviating by ± 1.37 mm.

A series of ten EAC devices was tested for the capability to pressurize the bladder for the CUS probe. All devices, except one device, could pressurize the system up to 150 mmHg, which corresponds to the maximum pressure specified in the requirements for the CUS method. The capability of the fully integrated CUS probes was verified using a stable silicone tissue phantom. These tests confirmed high repeatability and consistency in compression performance, with maximum pressures of 149–150 mmHg and tissue strain responses in the range of 13–15% across all evaluated units.

A series of ten EAC devices was tested for the capability to quickly depressurize the bladder for the VOP method. The pressure release time from 100 mmHg to 5 mmHg was approximately 0.4 s, demonstrating suitability for implementation of the VOP method.

The integration of an ultrasonography transducer into an automated wearable increased the number of product redesigns required by industry partners. Finalizing the WP3, the newly developed flexible C-shaped wearable accommodates the ultrasound probe and firmly holds it in place. The flexibility of the partners and strong inter-institutional collaboration within WP3.6 enabled the development of a body-mounted final probe for automated compression ultrasonography.